

Structural Investigations of Co(III) and Rh(III) Complexes of α -Benzilmonoxime*

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Magnetic and spectral data suggest that $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ are octahedral and have five-membered chelated ring structures involving bonding through oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms

TRIS-(α -benzilmonoximate) cobalt(III), $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$, has been assigned the structure I by Taylor and Ewbank¹, while Pfeiffer and Richarz² have suggested its representation by the structure II

However, its structure has not been studied by physico-chemical methods. In the present study the structures of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ have been investigated by magnetic measurements and NMR, IR, visible and uv spectroscopy. The synthesis of $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ has not been reported earlier in the literature.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents used were of A R grade α -Benzilmonoxime (HBMO) and $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ were prepared by the methods recommended by Welcher³. $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ was further purified by recrystallization from chloroform and analysed (Required for $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ Co-8.06%, C-68.96%, H-4.10%, N-5.74%, Found Co-8.09%, C-67.98%, H-4.30%, N-5.70%). $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ was prepared by adding a solution of 0.26 g of HBMO in 30 ml of ethanol to 10 ml of 1% solution of RhCl_3 in aqueous hydrochloric acid. A brick-red coloured complex was obtained. It was separated, recrystallised twice from benzene, dried at 110° and analysed for Rh, C, H and N (Required for $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ Rh-13.28%, C-64.88%, H-3.87%, N-5.42%, Found Rh-13.32%, C-64.00%, H-3.90%, N-5.40%).

Instruments employed are described elsewhere^{4,5}. Ethylenedibromide was used as a solvent in the determination of molecular weight of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ by the freezing point depression method.

Results and Discussion

$\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ (red) and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ (brick-red)

are soluble in organic solvents, insoluble in water and nonionic in nitrobenzene solution. The former is monomeric in ethylenedibromide solution. Both the complexes are diamagnetic, indicating octahedral structure involving $d^2 sp^3$ hybridisation.

The PMR spectrum (Fig 1) of HBMO in dioxane exhibits a peak at -1.1τ (with respect to TMS) which is assigned to the =NOH group. Two bands near 1.70τ and 2.20τ are attributed to proton resonance signals from $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ group. $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ in CDCl_3 reveals these bands at 2.67τ and 2.70τ , while $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ in CDCl_3 exhibits them at 2.69τ and 2.73τ . The metal complexes do not show a signal due to the =NOH group suggesting the replacement of the oxime proton by the metal.

Co^{59} resonance signal (Fig 2) in CDCl_3 solution of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ is observed at a slightly higher field from that of tris-(ethylenediamine) cobalt(III) and is away from that of tris-(acetylacetonato) cobalt(III). Considering the relation between the chemical shift and the ligand field strength shown by Griffith and Orgel⁶, it is inferred that the ligand field strength of anion BMO^- is higher than that of ethylenediamine. The structure I for $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ would imply that the ligand field due to the anion BMO^- should be close to that of acetylacetonate ion and much less than that of ethylenediamine. The chemical shift of Co^{59} in $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ seems to support the structure II proposed by Pfeiffer and Richarz.

The infra-red spectra of the reagent α -benzilmonoxime (HBMO), partially deuterated HBMO, $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ in CsBr disc have been examined in the region $4000-250\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The broad band around 3440 cm^{-1} in HBMO is assigned to hydrogen bonded $-\text{OH}$ stretching frequency (Fig 3). This assignment is further confirmed by the appearance of a new band at 2508 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the partially deuterated HBMO. One of the important features of the infra-red spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ is the absence of OH-stretching frequency in the region $3600-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig 4). This suggests that the hydrogen of the oxime group $-\text{NOH}$ is replaced by the metal atom.

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Fig 1 PMR spectra of (A) HBMO (B) $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and (C) $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$

Fig 2 NMR spectrum of Co in a CDCl_3 solution of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$

on complexation, which is in good agreement with the results of PMR studies. The two complexes HBMO and deuterated HBMO exhibit C=H stretching frequency near 3080 cm^{-1} . The bands due to the monosubstituted phenyl in HBMO appear at 1595 cm^{-1} , 1572 cm^{-1} , 1495 cm^{-1} , 1440 cm^{-1} , 762 cm^{-1} and 688 cm^{-1} . These bands are observed more or less at the same position in the spectra of deuterated HBMO, $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$.

The strong absorption at 1675 cm^{-1} in HBMO is not shifted on deuteration and therefore it is assigned to C=O of an aromatic ketone. The peak near 1650 cm^{-1} is attributed to C=N stretching frequency. The two bands at 1608 cm^{-1} and 1515 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ may be attributed to perturbed C=O and/or C=N stretching frequencies. This implies that the

complexation leads to the bonding through oxygen and nitrogen atoms of HBMO as expected on the basis of the five membered ring structure II. The spectrum of $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ is similar to that of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$, except that it shows two additional bands at 1640 cm^{-1} and 1670 cm^{-1} . The reasons for their presence are not obvious. One possibility is that one of the bands is associated with $-\text{C}=\text{C}-$ stretching frequency which may arise due to the structure III. Apparently

these bands are very weak in $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$.

The structures II and III suggest the presence of

Fig 3 Infrared Absorption Spectra of α -Benzilmonoxime (—) and Deuterated α -Benzilmonoxime (- -)

Fig 4 Infrared Absorption Spectra of Co(BMO)₃ (—) Complex and Rh(BMO)₃ (- -) Complex

N→O, N=O and metal-nitrogen stretching frequencies. The bands at 1215 cm⁻¹ and 1945 cm⁻¹ in HBMO are not shifted on deuteration and so they are assigned to N—O stretching. These bands are shifted respectively to 1268 cm⁻¹ and 1182–1184 cm⁻¹ in Co(BMO)₃ and Rh(BMO)₃, which suggests increase in the double bond character of N—O linkage on complex formation. This is consistent with the five-

membered ring structures II & III. The six-membered ring structure I proposed by Taylor and Ewbank would require the reduction of the double bond character of the N—O linkage due to the formation of M—O and the shift of N—O frequency towards the lower wavenumber side.

Both Co(BMO)₃ and Rh(BMO)₃ exhibit a

number of bands in the range of $700\text{-}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is difficult to assign them without any ambiguity, because HBMO also shows bands in this region.

FIG 5 ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF α -BENZILMONOXIME IN
 1) 0.01N NaOH SOLUTION (○-○-○)
 2) METHANOL SOLUTION (×-×-×)

The ultra-violet spectrum of HBMO in methanol solution exhibits a high intensity absorption maximum at 40.00 kK ($\epsilon = 22,800$), which is attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. In 0.1 N NaOH it reveals a shoulder near 34.48 kK in addition to the strong band at 40.00 kK ($\epsilon = 18,200$) (Fig. 5). Both $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ in methanol exhibit a $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition band in the ligand near 40.00 kK , the molar extinction coefficients being $31,700$ and $37,600$ respectively (Fig. 6). $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ shows an intense absorption maximum at 34.48 kK ($\epsilon = 30,800$) which may also be due to a $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the ligand. This band is not observed in the spectrum of $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$.

The charge transfer transitions in $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ seem to appear as a broad maximum in the region $23.81\text{-}29.85\text{ kK}$. The d-d transitions in these complexes are not observed because they are probably obscured by the tail-end of the high intensity charge transfer bands. The reflectance spectra of the complexes reveal a peak in the region $33.33\text{-}38.46\text{ kK}$ in addition to a diffuse maximum in the range $20.00\text{-}28.57\text{ kK}$ (Fig 7).

Fig 6. Electronic Spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{BMO})_3$ (○-○-○) and $\text{Rh}(\text{BMO})_3$ (△-△-△) in methanol.

Fig 7. Reflectance Spectra of Co(BMO)₃ Complex (o-o-o) and Rh(BMO)₃ Complex (Δ-Δ-Δ)

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